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A new perspective on geohazards assessment: leveraging gigapixel imaging technique

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Abstract—The growing frequency of geohazards such as landslides, rockfalls, and slope instabilities, often intensified by climate change and human activities, underscores the urgent need for effective assessment and monitoring tools. Conventional remote sensing techniques like LiDAR, aerial photogrammetry, and satellite interferometry (InSAR) often rely on substantial financial and technical resources, which limit their accessibility. In response, Gigapixel imaging emerges as an innovative and cost-effective alternative, offering ultra-high-resolution visual data to support geohazard assessment while raising awareness among stakeholders and the public. The system used captures hundreds of partially overlapping images in sequence using a robotic head, effectively minimizing parallax errors. With accurate image stitching, it becomes possible to reconstruct an exceptionally detailed 2D gigapixel image. Also, the use of well-known photogrammetric technique allows the generation of 3D models from very high-quality images obtaining Very-High Resolution products. The CDRI's fellowship GIGA² - Gigapixel Imaging for Geohazards Assessment and Awareness is aimed at exploring the practical implications of integrating Gigapixel imaging into geohazard monitoring. Beyond its technical advantages, it promotes inclusivity in geoscience by providing an accessible and impactful tool for communicating risks and fostering preparedness. By bridging the gap between advanced technology and practical applications, Gigapixel imaging offers a promising pathway for enhancing geohazard assessment and resilience in vulnerable areas.

I. INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, many geological representations are available, with the majority existing in 2D formats (e.g., geological maps), and only a sparse few in 3D formats (e.g., point clouds, block diagrams, etc.). Enhancing geological mapping poses a challenge, demanding more precise data collection and the seamless integration of information for the development of improved 3D

models. Advancements in remote sensing, computer vision, and photogrammetry have significantly enhanced our ability to analyze and interpret geohazards, enabling early warnings and informed decision-making. Terrestrial remote techniques providing high-resolution 3D products for geohazard mapping and monitoring have undergone extensive testing, offering detailed insights into processes such as landslides, rockfalls, slope instabilities, and subsidence, especially where there is poor site accessibility. Despite this, their widespread usage remains limited. Indeed, conventional remote sensing techniques like LiDAR, aerial photogrammetry, and satellite interferometry (InSAR) often offer limited accessibility due to substantial financial and technical requirements, especially in Low-Income Countries. Gigapixel imaging could become a valid and cost-effective alternative. This technique captures ultra-high-definition optical images composed of billions of pixels. It allows combination with photogrammetric and imaging techniques like Structure from Motion (SfM) and Image stitching. This approach enables the creation of detailed two- and three-dimensional representations of geological features and processes which are strongly affected by spatial variability. These capabilities make it a versatile tool for geotechnical monitoring, back-analysis support tool, geoscience education, and public awareness campaigns [e.g., 1, 2, 3, 4, 5].

For instance, the ultra-detailed data produced by Gigapixel imaging can effectively convey geohazard risks to policymakers and local communities, enhancing understanding and preparedness. Its affordability and ease of use further broaden its appeal, making it accessible to researchers, professionals, public agencies, and NGOs.

Within this context, the CDRI (Coalition for Disaster Resilient Infrastructures) fellowship named “GIGA²” is aimed at exploring practical uses and implications of integrating Gigapixel imaging

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into more conventional monitoring and site assessment, through study sites presenting different geohazard typologies.

Following, Section 2 describes the experimental setup, the methods and instruments used, and the processing procedures. Section 3 introduces the selected case studies identified in the context of this project. Finally, Section 4 summarizes the gained knowledge, highlights the main limitations of the presented approach, and provides an outlook for future work.

II. METODOLOGY

Gigapixel images consisting of digital images comprised of billions of pixels or more. While typical modern cameras boast sensors with over 20 million pixels (20MP), they fall short of directly creating Gigapixel images. However, leveraging innovative technologies and instruments (e.g., GigaPan) enables achieving remarkable results. More in detail, the proposed research is performed by coupling Image stitching with Structure from Motion (SfM) photogrammetric technique to analyse geohazards within complex contexts obtaining Very-High Resolution products (e.g. Point Cloud). In other words, the integration of such techniques allows the generation of 3D models from very high-quality images. This also allows assessing scenarios from remote locations (e.g. 1km away) ensuring the safety of the technicians involved. Moreover, such Gigapixel images, if acquired in different time periods, can also be compared by using Digital Image Correlation (DIC) techniques.

Therefore, this study is based on a mixed-method research methodology which uses the characteristics of both quantitative and qualitative research methodologies in the same study. This is because by combining the two types of data (quantitative and qualitative) it is possible to benefit from both the detailed and contextualized insights of qualitative data (e.g., gigapixel images and its geological interpretation) and quantitative data (e.g., point clouds and geo-structural analysis). Image acquisition is performed through a 20MP DSLR camera equipped with a telephoto zoom lens (200-500mm). This acquisition stage is performed by means of robotic mounts empower DSLR camera to take thousands of aligned and overlaid photos, which are combined and stitched to create a single highly defined image allowing the view of many details.

III. PRACTICAL APPLICATION AND IMPLICATIONS

The Gigapixel approach has various practical applications depending on the context where it is used as it allows 3D information to be obtained from 2D image sequences. Three main geohazards are addressed in the present research work: rockfalls, shallow landslides and debris flow. Study sites have been selected as part of research projects currently in progress and which directly involve the Geological Survey of Italy (ISPRA, Italian Institute for Environmental Protection and Research). Also, in order to make the experiment more efficient also from a logistical point of view,

nearby sites within a radius of 150 km were considered (Figure 1). However, sites with very different conditions in terms of geological setting, topography and geohazards and exposed value were identified (Table I).

Figure 1. Location of the three study sites used in this work.

TABLE I. DRIVING PARAMETERS FOR THE SELECTION OF STUDY SITES.

	Study sites		
	<i>Monte Mario (Roma)</i>	<i>Santuario S. Trinità (Vallepietra)</i>	<i>Nottoria (Norcia)</i>
Geohazards	Rainfall-triggered shallow landslide	Rockfall	Debris flow
Exposed items	Densely populated urban area	Historical shrine	Mountain village
Main stakeholders	Civil Protection Department (Municipality of Rome)	Municipality of Vallepietra	Local university

As regards the rockfall case study (Santuario S. Trinità, Vallepietra), a discontinuity set detection and assessment have been carried out from a very high-resolution point cloud. Such a point cloud has been generated starting from 3 Gigapixel

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acquisitions, the results of which have been in turn processed through SfM technique. Therefore, by using the open-source software Discontinuity Set Extractor (DSE) which enables the assessment of the joint families' orientation and spacing (Figure 2b), the jointed rock wall has been characterized [6]. Traditional geological survey allowed to confirm data obtained from images (Figure 2a). Such quantitative representation of the rock-wall permitted building a 3D model in RocScience finite element code, considering the discontinuities' geometry (Figure 3). Rock materials and joints were attributed to the respective stiffness and strength properties evaluated by a rock mechanics laboratory and field investigation [7].

Figure 2. a) Jointed rock-wall under study, with rock joints identification by a field survey, b) Joint families detected from DSE software.

For the represented case, a boundary condition of null displacements only was imposed on the bottom and on the two smaller lateral faces of the model. This allowed us to represent continuity with the adjacent rock-wall portions and with the intact background, in order to limit the extent of the 3D model and to reduce the computational effort. A stability analysis was conducted, revealing the main rockfall kinematics (wedge failure, Figure 3) to be expected given the discontinuities orientations and the mechanical properties of the rock mass. This model could be

also used to perform back-analyses referring to past rockfall events within the monitored area.

Within the shallow landslide case (Monte Mario, Roma), from a Digital Surface Model (DSM) derived from gigapixel photogrammetry a 2-dimensional simulation with limit equilibrium and finite element models have been performed by transposing the geological-technical slope model to a numerical model.

Finally, a debris flow case (Nottoria, Norcia) has been analyzed: in this case, given the presence of dense vegetation, Gigapixel images were used for a qualitative assessment of the scenario investigated (e.g., shape detection, vegetation regrowth, presence of debris, etc.). Using the approach presented in this paper, an attempt was made to create a Digital Terrain Model (DTM) and then derive some of the main Geomorphic indexes (e.g. Terrain Ruggedness Index, Slope, Valley Depth, etc.). Due to the noisy data, the data are not considered to be reliable.

Figure 3. Joint sets used in the model and results from the FEM stability analysis.

IV. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

The photogrammetric processing of Gigapixel data represents an unconventional approach in the analysis for geohazard assessment. Given its low cost and ease of deployment and use, it would be particularly relevant for the safety of linear infrastructure including roads, railways, and pipelines, with a special focus on

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mountainous regions. The main limitation is due to the nature of the photographic sensor: with low light conditions expect poor results. Although tests have been carried out at multiple sites affected by different geohazards, the proposed approach can be expected to have further limitations due to the geometry of the survey. For example, in the case of considerable sensor-scenario distances, or a limited field of view due to shadow areas, the acquisition of the data and therefore the creation of a three-dimensional model would be of poor definition or with sectors with missing data (e.g., holes) respectively.

Both new technology and techniques tested and validated in this project and still underestimated in the field of geosciences, fully fall within the field of terrestrial remote sensing. The photogrammetric processing of Gigapixel data would represent an innovative turning point in quantitative analysis for geohazard assessment. Potentially, the results achieved during the project could open new lines of research and experiments in the field of terrestrial remote sensing using optical sensors. In any case, the products that will be achieved and their impact will be easily assessable as they are basic products that are usually used in professional work. Potential stakeholders are researchers, technologists as well as practitioners. Further potential implementation will concern the use of thermal sensors (e.g. thermal cameras) which the proponents undertake to evaluate as a further test to be carried out on the field.

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